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DEPARTMENT OF CIVIL ENGINEERING**

MANUFACTURING OF LOW COST, ECO-FRIENDLY TERRAZZO TILE MADE IN RECYCLING OF GLASS, PLASTIC, SAND, LIME AND CLAY.

A dissertation presented in partial fulfillment of the requirements for award of a Bachelor's of Science with Honors in Civil Engineering.

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Musanze, July 2025

DECLARATION OF ORIGINALITY

I declare that the project entitled “Manufacturing of low cost, eco-friendly Terrazzo Tile made in recycling of glass, plastic, sand, lime and clay is my original work and has never been submitted to any University or other higher learning Institutions. I therefore declare that this work is my own for the partial fulfillment of the requirement for the degree of bachelor science in civil engineering department at Ines-Ruhengeri. It is my own work whereby other scholars’ writings were cited and references provided. I thus declare that this work is my own work and was completed successfully under the supervisor Eng. STRATON TUYIZERE.

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APPROVAL

This is to certify that this dissertation work entitled " Manufacturing of low cost, eco-friendly Terrazzo tile made in recycling of glass, plastic, sand, lime and clay. is an original study conducted by NGABONZIZA Emile and has been submitted with the approval of supervisor under his supervision and guidance.

Supervisor's name: Eng. Straton TUYIZERE

Supervisor's signature

Submission date

DEDICATION

To almighty God for his powerful
protection and guidance

To my beloved parents

To my beloved classmates

To all my lecturers

To the government of Rwanda

To the Institution of INES

RUHENGERI Staff

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Above all, it is important to thank Almighty God for his blessing up on this project from the start until end, for his protection and guiding each and every step in this study. May these simple words express respect to him. Special thanks are addressed to the government of Rwanda for encouraging quality education. Thank INES RUHENGARI entire staff, in particular to the department of civil engineering. The realization of this work is a result of their combined efforts in one way or another. Furthermore, to thank institution body and its partners for their enormous contribution to the studies. Especially, special thanks go to family that gave me all necessary requirements that enabled me to complete this project. Finally, I extend all my thanks to my friends for their collaboration and provided material support to the writing of this dissertation. I extend my thanks to all people who have supported me during this work.

ABSTRACT

There is now a significant worldwide interest to solve the environmental problems caused by glass, plastics wastes and by collecting such waste can be recycled into some construction materials. This technology has been introduced in some developed countries by being used It on floors and wall finishes. this project promotes innovation in sustainable construction materials, encouraging the development of new and creative ways to utilize waste materials. thus, the result of water absorption capacity of a tile which has 25cm *20cm*1.5cm. has been obtained that is $1.70\pm 0.55\%$ while traditional terrazzo tile obtained $1.92\pm 0.37\%$, the international standard determines (ASTM) that absorption capacity of good terrazzo, when completely absorb water should not exceed 3%, this symbolize that a terrazzo tile made from a recycled glass, plastic waste ,cement, lime, sand and clay had less water absorption, the compressive strength test was performed to check the compressive resistance and it has proven that when we apply 2000KN at 19600 mm^2 but with different crushed glasses ratios such as (20%, 30%, 40%) compressive strengths in different curing period such as in 7 days, 14 days and 21 days so, in generally for compressive strength the minimum is $62.08\pm 0.62 \text{ N/mm}^2$ and maximum $72.06\pm 2.1 \text{ N/mm}^2$, for traditional terrazzo tile the compressive strength in different curing period such as in 7 days, 14 days and 21 days so, the minimum is 64.25 ± 1.3 and maximum $67.505\pm 0.81 \text{ N/mm}^2$ therefore, new terrazzo tile is strong and good compare to traditional tile according to the compressive strength results. Considering standards (such as ASTM C373) said that compressional strength below 20 MPa are classified as low-compressive strength and are considered highly affected to cracking and fail during installation.

the cost of manufactured terrazzo tile is low with respect to existing terrazzo tile where manufactured terrazzo tiles is proposed to be 30,000Rwf/m², while the local market price show that traditional terrazzo cost is 40,000Rwf/m² .and hence this type of new terrazzo tile is affordable due to its low cost with respect to other existing terrazzo materials also is feasible. By concluding, I recommend students to keep working on this project by having more information about other properties (like fire resistance, tensile tests and slip resistance Test of this new terrazzo tiles) which had been not tested because of lack of accessibility to outside laboratories.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

%	: Percentage
µm	: Micrometer
ASTM	: American Society for Testing Materials
Cr	: Chromium
EN	: European Norm known as European standard committee
Fe	: Iron
Fe ₂ O ₃	: Iron (III) oxide
G	: Gram
HDPE	: High-Density Polyethylene
INES- RUHENGARI	: Institut d'Enseignement Supérieur de Ruhengeri
IS	: Indian Standard
ISO	: International Organization for Standardization
Kg	: Kilogram
KN	: Kilo Newton
LCA	: Life Cycle Assessment
LDPE	: Low-Density Polyethylene
MgO	: Magnesia
Mm	: Millimeter
Mn	: Manganese
MnO	: Manganese Oxide
MPa	: Mega-pascal
MSW	: Municipal Solid Waste
N/m ²	: Newton/Millimeter square
PET	: Polyethylene terephthalate

PP	: Polypropylene
PPR	: Polypropylene random
PS	: Polystyrene
PVC	: Polyvinyl chloride
RWF	: Rwandan francs
SDGs	: Sustainable Development Goals
Ti	: Titanium
TiO ₂	: Titanium dioxide
USBRE	: United States Bureau of Reclamation's Engineering Geology
WAC	: Water Absorptivity percentage
Wt.%	: Weight Percent

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CHAPTER 1: GENERAL INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the study

Terrazzo is a low-maintenance, environmentally friendly material with optimum durability. Poured on the job site, terrazzo can consist of marble, quartz, granite aggregate, mother-of-pearl and/or pre-consumer and post-consumer recycled tile particles, porcelain and mirror chips, which are mixed with cement or epoxy and polished to produce a smooth, uniformly textured surface for floors, walls, stairs, curbs, counter-tops and ceilings(Cheever, 2014).plastic Waste Reduction by repurposing plastic waste, we can significantly reduce the amount of plastic that ends up in landfills and polluting our environment. This helps mitigate the harmful effects of plastic pollution on ecosystems and human health. developing Sustainable Solutions this project promotes innovation in sustainable construction practices, encouraging the development of new and creative ways to utilize waste materials(Bustillo Revuelta & Bustillo Revuelta, 2021).

Technological Advancements: The research and development involved in this project can lead to advancements in material science and manufacturing processes, benefiting various industries. the disposal of plastic waste has emerged as a pressing global issue, with specific relevance in Rwanda. According to, city-specific studies reveal that plastics constitute 1.5 to 7 percent of waste in Kigali, where waste generation reached 800tones per day in 2018. Projections suggest that Rwanda may generate 75,000 to 100,000tones of plastic waste annually by 2030. Millions of plastics find their way into landfills or natural ecosystems each year. These non-biodegradable materials persist for centuries, releasing harmful chemicals and micro-plastics that pose grave threats to wildlife and human health. Plastic recycling not only lessens landfill pressure but also conserves energy and raw materials needed for new plastic production(Lubogo, 2024).

The construction industry significantly contributes to global greenhouse gas emissions and resource depletion. Integrating sustainable building materials can profoundly mitigate the industry's environmental impact. Eco-friendly materials, produced from recycled plastics, grass not only aid in waste management but also curtail the demand for virgin material extraction and energy consumption. this project focuses on using recycled glass in the

manufacturing of eco-friendly terrazzo tiles in Rwanda. As the country moves to reduce plastic use, the demand for glass products has increased, leading to more available glass waste. Recycling this glass helps reduce environmental pollution and supports the circular economy. By incorporating crushed glass into terrazzo tiles, the project aims to produce cost-effective, durable, and visually appealing tiles while contributing to Rwanda's sustainability goals(Bustillo Revuelta & Bustillo Revuelta, 2021).

In terms of developing Rwandan citizens with improvement of different services for human being, such as healthy, environment protection, and providing construction materials made in Rwanda. This project deals with manufacturing strong terrazzo tile made from recycled wastes glasses Plastic.

1.2 Problem statement

The construction industry faces significant challenges related to environmental sustainability, resource depletion, and waste management. Traditional terrazzo tiles are made from a composite of decorative aggregates, such as marble, granite, quartz, or pearls, bound together by a matrix of either cement or epoxy resin, contribute to high carbon emissions and extensive resource consumption, exacerbating the global environmental crisis. Concurrently, the increasing volume of plastic and glasses waste poses a critical threat to ecosystems and public health, with millions of tons of plastic and glass entering landfills and oceans annually. Depending on the SDGs, article 13 of maintaining the environment(Doni et al., 2020).

This innovative project aims to develop eco-friendly terrazzo tiles by combining recycled plastic, glass, sand, lime, and clay with addition of little amount of cement to address environmental concerns in the construction industry. It focuses on ensuring reliable sourcing, material quality, sustainable manufacturing, and improved durability and aesthetics through optimized mixtures. The project also evaluates environmental impact, market acceptance, and compliance with regulations to support sustainable development and promote widespread adoption.

1.3. Research objective.

1.3.1 General objective

The main objective of this study is to use recycled glasses as replacement for conventional marble chips in terrazzo products and additional of crushed plastics powder as filler.

1.3.2. Specific Objectives

- a) To conduct performance tests such as water absorption and compressive strength tests on terrazzo flooring samples.
- b) To compare the performance characteristics of recycled glass and plastics crushed in terrazzo with traditional marble chip in terrazzo.
- c) To assess the cost of recycled glasses and plastics terrazzo tile products compared to traditional terrazzo tile.
- d) To know the environmental impact of traditional terrazzo tile production compared to recycled terrazzo tile.

1.4. Research questions

- a) How durable and resistant are terrazzo tiles made with recycled glass and plastic?
- b) How does recycled glass terrazzo compare to traditional marble chip terrazzo in strength and quality?
- c) What is the production cost of terrazzo tiles using recycled glass and plastic particles and traditional terrazzo tile production?
- d) What is the energy use, emissions, and waste impacts of producing recycled glass terrazzo tiles and traditional terrazzo tile?

1.5 Choice of the study

The study on the terrazzo tile production made from recycling of glass, plastic and clay, sand was conducted to address several challenges facing the construction industry in Rwanda. These challenges include high costs of building materials, environmental pollution from construction activities, low quantity of tiles, poor quality of building materials, and limited availability of sustainable and environmentally friendly building materials. The study aims to explore the potential of using locally available waste materials

such as glass, plastic and clay to produce tile that are durable, environmentally friendly, and of good quality.

The study strives to explore the feasibility of using commonly found local waste materials such as glass, plastic and clay in the production of durable, environmental-friendly, and quality tiles. With this, the study aims to enhance the sustainability and cost-effective.

1.6. Significance of the study

1.6.1. Personal benefits

This project is crucial important it helps researcher since it allows the researcher to get greater knowledge about construction materials through deep investigation and research. Through research involving recycled materials like glass, plastic, lime, clay, and sand, the researcher gains first -hand knowledges about green alternatives for building purposes. The study also provides the chance to asks some technical and research skills through experiential experimentation. Additionally, during the implementation stage, the study could be lucrative in a financial aspect, especially if it is marketable. Mostly, it works as both academic development and potential gains, which support in its individual development.

1.6.2. Social benefits

The research has many important social benefits. Firstly, on the level of innovation, it offers a new sustainable building material made from recycled wastes that can replace traditional materials and stimulate environmentally friendly building practices. Second, by recycling plastic wastes, glass wastes, and other types of waste materials, the project ensures clean and healthy urban environments in Rwanda, decreasing pollution and making Rwandan cities cleaner in general. Also, production and manufacturing of green terrazzo tiles can stimulate local industries and enhance employment opportunities, thereby adding to the economic growth in the construction sector. The project is therefore in line with national goals of sustainable development and conservation of the environment.

1.6.3. Environmental benefits

The project is very important crucial environmentally important since it addresses the rising issues of plastic and glasses wastes. One of the master key advantage is the prevention of soil and water contamination, which is the usually result of the indiscriminate dumping of plastic, glasses waste in landfills and natural environments. By converting plastics, glasses into useful construction materials like terrazzo tiles, the project prevents the harmful impact of these pollutants on the ecosystems. Additionally, it assists in protecting biodiversity by reducing the likelihood of animals and people unintentionally consuming wastes that lead to injury or fatality. Overall, the project supports environmental sustainability by transforming hazardous waste into an asset and protecting natural habitats from pollution-related harm.

1.7. Delimitation of study

The production of this tiles requires complex and wide study in various domains such as: water absorption, compressive strength, thickness swelling and estimating the cost required for the completion of the study. In that way this study was focus on water absorption and compressive test, cost of terrazzo tile, this study is limited on fire resistance, tensile test, slip resistances so those tests can be carried out once the study was implemented. The research was focused to the technical aspects of the production process, and was not cover marketing, sales, or other business-related aspects. Only glass, plastic, clay and sand were used as raw materials, and the study was conducted within a specific timeframe. These delimitations are important to ensure that the research is focused, achievable, and relevant to the intended audience.

1.8 Organization of project

This study was arranged into five chapters as follows

Chapter One: Introduced the topic and sets objectives and problem statement as well as scope for the report. Chapter Two: Reveals literature regarding to terrazzo tile from recycled wastes as material; the history and theory behind terrazzo tile and also outlined, few examples of some commonly used materials discussed. Chapter Three: Describes the

different types of materials to be used and tests to be performed. The process for compressive, water absorption, and environmental impact, methodology, applied in this study, is also outlined. Chapter Four: Showed analyses of the results obtained from experiment. And focused on analysis and interpretation of the results. chapter Five: discusses the observations made from chapter 4; Outlined final relevant conclusion derived from this study and provided recommendations on further studies/investigations to be made.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

Terrazzo tile has been a hard-wearing, beautiful floor finish for centuries. Traditionally, it consists of marble, granite, quartz, or pearls chips in a cementitious or resinous matrix. A number of studies confirm that the reasons valued for terrazzo are strength, durability, and easy maintenance. Traditional manufacturing methods conventionally depend on virgin raw material inputs, resulting in resource depletion and other environmental issue ,and researchers have included recycled materials in terrazzo compositions (Silvestre & Țîrcă, 2019).

Some of the prominent research topics for sustainable construction relate to the incorporation of waste glass and plastics as tile-manufacturing aggregates. In fact, experiments have proved that crushed glass can replace marble chippings without causing a noticeable decrease in strength. Besides this, it has also been tried to incorporate recycled plastics into composite materials for better resistance at impacts and reducing the overall weight. Studies have also highlighted that adequately treated and processed plastics can improve flexibility and thermal insulation in the building materials, thereby making them more versatile for various applications(Ezzeldin, 2021).

The waste plastic will be large in household time. In many countries the compositions of waste are Different, that the socioeconomic characters, waste management programs and consumption patterns affect it but generally the level of plastic in the waste composition is high.one of the largest components of plastic waste is polyethylene which is followed by polypropylene. Polyethylene terephthalate and Polystyrene. The large volume of materials required for construction is potentially a major area for the reuse of waste materials. Recycling the plastics has advantages since it is widely used and has a long service life, which means that the waste is being removed from the waste stream for a long period(Di *et al.*, 2021).

The role of binders like lime and clay in sustainable construction is also widely documented. Lime has been used in green building because it has low carbon emissions and heals itself. Recently, literature is coming out saying that lime-based binders produce tiles with high breathability and moisture regulation to improve indoor air quality. Likewise, clay is a naturally occurring material with low-energy processing. Therefore, clay has been experimented as a binder in tile formulation. From the environmental point of view, the inclusion of waste in terrazzo tiles will meet the objectives on alternative development for the whole world(Soni *et al.*, 2022).

2.2 Classification of engineering materials

One of the most challenging tasks of materials engineer is the proper selection of the material for a particular job, e.g., a particular component of a machine or structure. An engineer must be in a position to choose the optimum combination of properties in a material at the lowest possible cost without compromising the quality. Here's a detailed classification in this Table2.1.

Table 2.1:Engineering materials concerning to the project

Material types	Example in project	Key roles
Polymers	Recycled Plastic	Enhances, durability, impact resistance, and water resistance.
Ceramics	Clay, Sand	Provides, structural, strength and heat resistance.
Composites	Terrazzo Mix	Creates a sustainable, durable, and customization tile.
Glass	Recycled Glass	Improves, aesthetics, hardness, and scratch resistance, replace of marble chipping.
Binders	Lime	Acts as a binding agent, improving, durability and reducing cement use.
Cement	Binder	To improve strength, durability and acts as a binder.

In a technical study focused on the production of terrazzo tile made from a composite of plastic, glass, clay, lime and sand with a little amount of cement, it is essential to evaluate the engineering properties of the materials used. The process includes assessing their physical, mechanical, and thermal properties to ensure the tiles meet the necessary performance standards for construction applications. Below is a summary of the key properties and their significance in the context of tile production:

2.3 Type of Construction Material

Building structures are composed of various materials, often referred to as building materials or materials of construction. It is essential for builders whether architects, engineers, or contractors to thoroughly understand these materials. Knowledge of different materials, their properties, and uses for various purposes provides an important tool for

builders to achieve cost efficiency. Material costs in building projects range from 30 to 50 percent of the (Allen & Iano, 2019).

2.3.1 Plastics

Traditionally, cement or lime is used as a binder in terrazzo tiles, holding together aggregates like sand, crushed stone, and glass. However, recycled plastics (such as PET, HDPE, or PP) are being explored as an alternative void's filler. This is a promising approach that can reduce reliance on conventional of water absorption while promoting sustainability.

1. Understanding How Plastics Can Act as a filler of voids.

Plastics, particularly shredded or granular plastics, can be effective void fillers for green terrazzo tile production. Filling interstices between materials like sand and glass, plastics enhance packing density, lower porosity, and allow more effective compaction of the mix. Not only does this make the finished product more durable, it also saves on cost of production and allows for easier recycling of wastes. Plastics as fillers are helpful in the production of lightweight, strong, and environmentally friendly tiles without improving environmental degradation and also reactions.

2. Types of Plastics Suitable for Use as a filler of voids.

In the manufacturing of eco-friendly terrazzo tiles, recycled plastics can play a valuable role not just as binders, but also as fillers to occupy voids, reduce material costs, and improve certain physical properties. When selecting plastics for use as fillers, factors such as durability, environmental impact, and compatibility with other materials (like lime and sand) should be considered, as shown in this table 2.2.

Table 2.2:Types of plastics suitable for use as a filler of voids

Plastic Type	Suitability as Binder	Common Sources
PET (Polyethylene Terephthalate)	Good – Strong, but brittle	Water bottles, food containers
HDPE (High-Density Polyethylene)	Excellent – Flexible and durable	Milk jugs, detergent bottles
LDPE (Low-Density Polyethylene)	Moderate – Soft, but water resistant	Plastic bags, wrap films
PP (Polypropylene)	Very Good – Tough and impact-resistant	Bottle caps, food containers
Polystyrene (PS / EPS)	Very lightweight – brittle, Packaging foam, disposable utensils	Plastic forks, spoons, knives, plates, cups.

Polyethylene Terephthalate: sometimes absorbs odors and flavors from foods and drinks that are stored in them. Items made from this plastic are commonly recycled. PET: plastic is used to make many common household items like beverage bottles, medicine jars, rope, clothing and carpet fiber(Ajaj *et al.*, 2022).

High-Density Polyethylene: products are very safe and are not known to transmit any chemicals into foods or drinks. HDPE products are commonly recycled. Items made from plastic include containers for milk, motor oil, shampoos and conditioners, soap bottles, detergents, and bleaches. It is never safe to reuse an HDPE bottle as a food or drink container if it did not originally contain food or drink(Timms, 2021).

Low-Density Polyethylene (LDPE), however, However, because it is flexible and long-lasting, low-density polyethylene (LDPE) is also occasionally recycled and is a very healthy plastic. Because of its strength and inertness, LDPE is used in a wide range of

products, including cling film, sandwich bags, squeeze containers, and grocery bags.(Tan, 2016).

Polypropylene (PP) is renowned for its strength and resistance to higher temperatures, and it is occasionally recycled. Because of this, PP is perfect for producing products like yogurt pots, lunchboxes, prescription bottles, syrup bottles, and containers for margarine. Furthermore, PP is widely used to make plastic bottle caps because of its dependability and durability under a variety of temperature conditions.(Maddah, 2016).

Polystyrene (PS): is a type of plastic which, though widely recycled, is especially vexing to recycle. It is used in the production of many disposable items such as coffee cups, plastic food containers, plastic utensils, and packing foam since it is so light and an insulator. In addition, the SPI code 7 is used to identify miscellaneous plastic types that are outside of the scope of the other six codes. Plastics like Polycarbonate (PC) and Polylactide (PLA), which are difficult to recycle, fall under this category. Polycarbonate is strong and clear and is therefore used in items like baby bottles, compact discs, and medical storage containers. (Farrelly & Shaw, 2017).

PET are uses in the following activity: soft drink, water, cooking oil bottles, packaging trays, and frozen ready-meal trays, first-aid blankets, etc. HDPE is a solid material that can tolerate high temperatures and strong chemicals, is used in this action. Cleaning solution and soap containers, food and drink storage, shopping bags. PVC has low cost to produce and resistance to chemical and biological attack and is easy to work with and reshape it. PVC is used in making furniture, clothing, medical container and lightweight sheets, etc. LDPE at general living temperatures and is highly non-reactive material, which means it is one the most common plastics uses at moment.

Their common uses are trays, container, computer hardware casings and drink cartons. PP is strong and flexible, polypropylene is very hard-wearing plastic that, when is melted one of the most effective materials for injection molding. It has quite a high tolerance to high temperatures, relatives to other plastics and is consider to be food safe materials. It is used clothing, surgery tools and straws, crisp bags, food container, lunch box, bottle cape, packing tape, as shown in this figure2.1(Srinivasan *et al.*, 2017).

Figure 2.1: Plastic wastes in Nduba collection wastes

2.4. Sands

Sand is a naturally occurring granular material, which is composed of mineral particles and finely divided material. The composition of sand varies depending on the local rock conditions and sources, but the most common constituent of sand in inland continental settings and non-tropical coastal regions is silica dioxide (SiO_2) in the form of quartz. The second commonly used sand is calcium carbonate, for example aragonite, which has mostly been created over the past half billion years by various forms of life, like coral and shellfish. Sand is now used extensively in all construction processes(Aswath, 2013).

Sand is formed from rocky materials over thousands of years. Eroded sand is deposited on beaches, dunes, or deserts. The majority of the earth's surface consists of sand and quartz, usually composed of silica, and it also contains mineral particles and finely dispersed material. The chemical composition and physical characteristics of sand vary from one location to another. Non-tropical continental inland and coastal areas contain the greatest proportion of quartz silica dioxide (SiO_2) ("construction materials," 2018)).

Although sand can be classified in various ways, it is usually classified by origin (e.g., beach, river, marine, and desert), chemical composition (e.g., heavy mineral sand, silica sand, and gypsum sand), and grain size (coarse sand, 2–0.6 mm; medium sand, 0.6–0.2 mm; and fine sand, 0.2–0.06 mm). According to the United States Bureau of Reclamation's Engineering Geology (USBRE) Field Manual, sand is defined as rock particles that pass through a No. 4 (4.75 mm) sieve and are retained by a No. 200 (0.75 mm) sieve. Fine sand passes through a No. 40 (425- μm) sieve and is retained by a No. 200 (0.075 mm or 75- μm) sieve. Medium sand passes through a No. 10 (2.00 mm) sieve and is retained by a No. 40 (425- μm) sieve. Coarse sand passes through a No. 4 (4.75 mm) sieve and is retained by a No. 10 (2.00 mm) sieve. Sustainability 2022, 14, 6446 6 of 17 Due to its low cost, versatility, and ease of acquisition, sand is used globally in construct.

Figure 2.2: Different types of sand

Characteristic of sand that is suitable for use in manufacturing process of that terrazzo tile:

A clean, dry river fine sand (0.2-0.06 mm), free from impurities and other chemicals, free from the soil and grasses could be used. Sand should be clean, any particles disturbing the neutrality of it should not be there. The sand used should be a well-graded mixture from coarser to fine grains, complying with the requirements of IS 383 Latest edition or equivalent. There must not be the presence of the trace of earth units(Erickson, 2019).

Table 2.3:Types of sand material (Namjoo *et al.*, 2021)

Glass sand	Traces of human activity are visible almost everywhere. Even sand may sometimes contain artificial fragment in quantities that justify the creation of separate sand type.
Immature sand	Sand composed of the same minerals that made up its parent rocks.
Gypsum sand	A rare sand type composed of gypsum grains
Silica sand	Silica sand is almost pure quartz
Mixed carbonate-silicate sand	Some sand samples are mixed of organic and inorganic sand grains.
Continental sand	The name says that all. This sand is common weathering product the continental landmasses.
Quartz sand	Quartz is the most common sand forming mineral. This sand type consists little else than this mineral
River sand	Sand is naturally occurring granular material, which is composed of mineral particles and finely divided material. The composition of sand varies depending on the local rock Conditions and sources, but the most constituent of sand in inland continental settings and non-tropical coastal region is silica dioxide (SiO ₂) in the form of quartz.

	<p>The second commonly used sand is the calcium carbonate, for example aragonite, which has mostly been created, over the past half billion years, by various forms of life, like coral and shellfish. Sand is now used in all the construction process</p>
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2.4.1. Uses of sand

Sand is used for several key construction elements: it is used for drainage and terrain preparation when making foundation of the structure it is used in landscaping for drainage to prevent clogging of drainage pipes as a natural filtering material, sand is used in levelling of uneven surfaces and cracked terrain, in making concrete sand is often principal component of this critical construction material(Arulmoly *et al.*, 2022).

2.5. Glass

Glasses are brittle substance; typically, transparent made by fusing sand with soda and lime and cooling it rapidly. Glasses used to make windows, drinking containers and other materials(Axinte, 2011). glass is found in municipal solid waste (MSW), primarily in the form of containers such as beer and soft drink bottles; wine and liquor bottles; bottle and jars for food, cosmetics and other products. Although most of the data is on glass containers, this analysis also considers glass materials in durable goods like tiles, furniture, appliances, and consumer electronics.

There are two types of waste glasses which are colored and colorless. Most colorless waste glasses are recycled effectively. Colored waste glasses with their low recycling rate are generally dumped into landfill sites as mentioned in table2.4. However, with the shortage of landfill sites, land filling is becoming more difficult(Pahlevani & Sahajwalla, 2018).

Table 2.4: Types of glasses and their main uses

N ^o	Main types	Main uses
1	Soda lime glasses	Used for making bottles and jars tableware
2	Lead glasses	Making tableware, television screen and display screen equipment
3	Borosilicate glasses	Making glass fiber wood insulation, ovenware
4	Technical glasses	Scientific frits, optical

The chemical composition of Glasses can vary depending on their specific type and composition. Here is a general overview of their chemical composition and its types which are:

Soda-lime Glass: The most common type of glass is soda-lime glass, composed of silica (SiO_2), soda (Na_2O), and lime (CaO). It may also contain small amounts of other oxides like alumina (Al_2O_3) or magnesia (MgO)(Yunusa, 2024).

Borosilicate Glass: Borosilicate glass is made by adding boron oxide (B_2O_3) to the mixture of silica, soda, and lime. It has a higher resistance to thermal expansion and is commonly used in laboratory glassware and heat-resistant glass products(Youngman, 2021).

Lead Glass: Lead glass, also known as crystal, is made by adding lead oxide (PbO) to the mixture of silica, soda, and lime. It has a higher refractive index, resulting in its characteristic brilliance. It is commonly used in fine glassware and decorative objects(Basu & Sarkar, 2019).

2.5.1. Properties of glasses

Physical properties

Brittleness: Glass is a brittle material that can break or shatter easily. brittle glass, once crushed and polished, produces sharp-edged, reflective pieces that enhance the visual appearance of terrazzo tiles and strength. The fragments can catch light and add a sparkle or shine to the tile surface, making the product more attractive for interior use(Binggeli, 2008).

Hardness: Glass is known for its hardness, making it a durable and scratch-resistant material in many applications. However, when compared to certain metals like hardened steel or ceramics such as alumina or silicon carbide, glass is relatively less hard. While it can resist surface abrasion and maintain clarity under normal use, it is also more brittle and prone to cracking or shattering under impact. This balance of hardness and brittleness makes glass an ideal material for terrazzo tiles, where its hardness contributes to wear resistance and aesthetic appeal, but it must be carefully combined with other materials to improve toughness and structural integrity(Roshan *et al.*, 2024).

Chemical properties of glass

Inertness: Glass is inert chemically, meaning that it will not easily react with acids, alkalis, or water due to the stable matrix of silica. This is helpful in the sense that it makes it an ideal candidate to be incorporated into terrazzo tiles since it will not react with binders like lime or clay and helps in overall stability and durability of the product.

Recycled glass does not absorb any water or release volatile toxic chemicals and therefore is secure, eco-friendly, and durable.

Corrosion resistance: Glass is usually highly resistant to corrosion by most acids, alkalis, and other corrosive materials that may normally be found in the air or in building materials. Its dense and non-porous character and the close chemical bonds between its components, primarily silica, are responsible for this resistance. Glass does not degrade, rust, or react even under extended exposure to water, chemicals, or air contaminants. This property also makes it an excellent material to utilize where stability to chemicals and

long-term durability are essential, such as in green terrazzo tiles. Corrosion resistance also guarantees that neither the appearance nor strength of the tile is compromised, even in extreme or exposed condition (Tournié et al., 2008) Thermal stability: Glass has good thermal stability, i.e., the capability to endure high temperatures without warping, melting, or undergoing deep-seated chemical changes.

This characteristic is due to its strong atomic bonds and dense silica network, which allow it to withstand deformation even under thermal stress. Due to this reason, glass does not readily expand or crack or lose its properties when exposed to heat, thereby being suitable for use in applications that could subject it to temperature fluctuation. This thermal stability in terrazzo tile production enables recycled glass to maintain its shape and functionality when producing and for the life of the tile(Xia *et al.*, 2023).

2.5.2 Sound and thermal properties of glasses

Thermal conductivity: Glass has a high thermal conductivity, meaning it can conduct heat easily. This property can result in glass surfaces quickly becoming hot or cold based on the surrounding temperature.

Sound insulation: Glass is a poor sound insulator and does not effectively block or absorb sound waves. It allows sound to pass through easily, leading to poor soundproofing qualities.

2.5.3 Mechanical properties of glasses

Strength: Glass is brittle and has limited tensile strength, meaning it is prone to breakage under tension. However, its compressive strength is high, allowing it to withstand considerable pressure.

Transparency: Glass is transparent, allowing light to pass through. It is also available in various colors and finishes.

2.5.4 Uses of glasses

Glass is widely used in windows, doors, and architectural structures to allow natural light into spaces. It is also used in the production of containers, mirrors, and other decorative construction objects. The image shows a large pile of waste glass bottles, which highlights the potential for recycling glass in innovative ways. For example, recycled glass can be crushed and used as an aggregate in construction materials such as terrazzo tiles, concrete, and paving blocks. This not only helps reduce environmental waste but also supports sustainable building practices as shown in the figure2.3:

Figure 2.3: Industrial glasses waste in the environment(Gaur *et al.*, 2020)

2.6 Lime

Lime is an inorganic material composed primarily of calcium oxides and hydroxides, like calcium hydroxide. lime used in building materials is broadly classified as "pure", "hydraulic", and "poor" lime; can be natural or artificial; and may be further identified by its magnesium content such as dolomitic or magnesium lime. Used for floors, tabby concrete, whitewash, silicate mineral paint, and limestone blocks which may be of many types. The qualities of the many types of processed lime affect how they are used. The Romans used two types of lime mortar to make Roman concrete, which allowed them to revolutionize architecture, sometimes called the Concrete revolution(Campanella, 2008) .

2.6.1 Hydrated lime uses

Plasticizer: Lime acts as a plasticizer in the terrazzo mix, enhancing workability and ease of handling. It improves the flow and consistency of the mix, making it easier to spread and work with during installation.

Improved Bonding: Lime helps improve the bond between the cementation's binder (such as white cement) and the aggregates in the terrazzo mix. This enhanced bonding contributes to the overall strength and durability of the terrazzo surface.

Reduction of Shrinkage Cracks: Lime can reduce the risk of shrinkage cracks in the terrazzo by controlling the rate at which the mix dries. This is especially important in large terrazzo installations where cracking can be a concern.

Aesthetic Benefits: Lime can help achieve a desirable aesthetic in terrazzo projects. It can enhance the finish and texture of the surface, making it more visually appealing, especially in decorative and architectural applications(Schittich, 2012).

In summary, lime used in terrazzo to enhance workability, improve bonding, reduce shrinkage cracks, achieve a polished finish, and enhance overall durability. Its use can contribute to the success and longevity of terrazzo project, particularly in achieving a visually appealing and structurally sound final surface.

2.7 Clay

Clay is a natural, earthy material that is composed primarily of fine-grained minerals. It is known for its plasticity when wet, which means it can be easily molded and shaped. When dried or fired, clay becomes hard and brittle. It is widely used in various applications such as pottery and ceramics

Figure 2.4: Clay Image

2.7.1 Composition of Clay

A technical study on the production of tiles made from a mixture of plastic and glasses wastes, clay, sand and lime involve analyzing the composition and properties of each material to understand their suitability for tile manufacturing. Clay, as a primary component, provides plasticity and binding properties essential for forming the tile shape. Its composition, including the types and proportions of clay minerals present, affects the final characteristics of the tile, such as its strength, color, and porosity, River sand serves as an aggregate, contributing to the tile's structure and texture. Its particle size distribution, mineral composition, and cleanliness are critical factors influencing the tile's mechanical properties and surface finish. Additionally, the presence of impurities in river sand may impact the firing process during tile production (Fontes, 2018).

Plastic, likely in the form of recycled plastic waste, introduces sustainability aspects to the tile manufacturing process. However, its incorporation requires a thorough examination of its compatibility with clay and sand, as well as its impact on the tile's properties and environmental footprint. Factors such as plastic type, particle size, and melting behavior need consideration to ensure proper mixing and homogeneity in the tile composition. The technical study would involve conducting experiments to determine the optimal mixture proportions of clay, sand, and plastic, as well as the processing parameters (e.g., mixing time, compaction pressure) to achieve desired tile properties (Dhawan *et al.*, 2019).

Types of Clay

Clay is a versatile natural material with various types distinguished by their mineral composition, properties, and geological origins. Among the commonly recognized types of clay are kaolinite, montmorillonite and bentonite(Kumari & Mohan, 2021).

Kaolinite clay, named after the Chinese village of Kaolin where it was originally mined, is characterized by its pure white color and fine particle size. It is one of the most commonly found clay minerals and is used extensively in the ceramics industry for making porcelain and fine China due to its high plasticity and low iron content

Montmorillonite clay, belonging to the smectite group of clays, is known for its exceptional swelling properties when hydrated. It exhibits a high cation exchange capacity, making it useful in various industrial applications such as drilling muds, cat litter, and as a binder in foundry molds

Illite clay, is widely used in the production of bricks, tiles, and as a drilling fluid additive due to its low plasticity and good binding properties.

2.8 Tiles

Tiles are flat, typically rectangular or square pieces made from materials such as ceramic, stone, or used to cover surfaces like floors, walls, and roofs, providing durability, aesthetic appeal, and ease of maintenance, they are applied by pouring a standard concrete foundation, spreading concrete on top, and then laying the tiles in the desired pattern. Tiles can be used to make roads, walkways and other outdoor platforms knowing that are different with terrazzo tile(Petravic & Bailey, 2015).

2.8.1 Types of Tiles

There are several types of tiles, each with unique properties and applications:

Ceramic Tiles: Made from clay that is baked at high temperatures. They are available in glazed and unglazed varieties. Glazed ceramic tiles have a coating that makes them more resistant to stains and moisture, while unglazed tiles are more slip-resistant

Porcelain Tiles: A subtype of ceramic tiles, porcelain tiles are made from denser clay and fired at higher temperatures, making them more durable and water-resistant. They are ideal for high-traffic areas and outdoor use.

Natural Stone Tiles: These include marble, granite, slate, and limestone. Natural stone tiles are highly valued for their unique textures and natural beauty. Each stone type has specific characteristics: marble is known for its elegance, granite for its durability, slate for its rustic look, and limestone for its natural warmth.

Glass Tiles: Made from thin pieces of glass with translucent glaze. They are commonly used in backsplashes, accent walls, and swimming pools due to their vibrant colors and reflective properties

Cement Tiles: Also known as hydraulic tiles, these are hands made tiles known for their durability and customizability. They are often used for decorative flooring.

Mosaic Tiles: Small tiles made from ceramic, glass, or stone, used to create intricate patterns and designs. They are often used in backsplashes, shower floors, and decorative wall features

2.8.2 Composition of Tiles

The composition of tiles varies depending on the type. Ceramic and porcelain tiles are primarily made from clay mixed with other minerals and water. The mixture is shaped, dried, and then fired in a kiln at high temperatures. The firing process creates a hard, durable surface. Natural stone tiles are cut and polished from large slabs of stone, each type having a unique mineral composition that gives it distinctive properties. For example, marble is composed primarily of calcite, granite is rich in quartz and feldspar, and slate is formed from clay and volcanic ash. Glass tiles are made by melting glass and shaping it into thin pieces. The addition of metal oxides can create a variety of colors. Cement tiles are made from a mixture of cement, sand, and pigments, which are pressed into molds and cured (Galos, 2011).

2.8.3 Applications of Tiles

Glass and ceramic tiles are typically installed for backs-plashes and shower walls. Roofing Certain tiles, such as slate and terracotta, are also installed for roofing due to their resistance to weather conditions and their attractiveness, Outdoor Areas Porcelain tiles and natural stone tiles are installed in outdoor spaces such as pool surround, patios, and walkways since they are resistant to weather conditions and durable.

Ornamental Details: Cement tiles and mosaic tiles of special design are generally utilized to develop ornamental details, i.e., designer designs and intricate patterns in interior and exterior spaces. Tiles are manufactured from a mixture of minerals, water, and clay, which are shaped and then subjected to high heat to create a firm, durable surface. They typically possess a glazed finish that is available in a wide range of color and design, hence making them ideal for use in functional and decorative applications. Ceramic tiles are generally used in covering floor, walls, and counter-tops because they are resistant, easy to maintain, and can be designed to fit any interior design (Van Lemmen, 2013).

2.9. Types of terrazzo tiles

Different type of terrazzo used in building construction are Cementations Terrazzo and epoxy Terrazzo:

Cementation Terrazzo (or cement terrazzo) is suited for renovation and exterior project, as it is heavier and thicker than epoxy-based terrazzo. It includes multiple terrazzo systems, including bonded, rustic, sand cushion, polyacrylate and monolithic. Cement terrazzo is better than epoxy-based terrazzo at withstanding steam cleaning, point loading, heavy traffic, and impacts (Abdal *et al.*, 2023).

Figure 2.5: Cementations Terrazzo pictures(Oates, 2008)

Epoxy Terrazzo Epoxy-based terrazzo gives a smooth, luxurious finish due to its thin-set system, and offers good design flexibility. Another advantage is faster application than cement terrazzo. Such speed permits a faster project turn around and is ideal for busy areas, such as shopping centers. This type of terrazzo is made from a two-component resin system and is extremely light. It can cure overnight and be ready for polishing the next day but is very expensive(Bustillo Revuelta & Bustillo Revuelta, 2021).

Figure 2.6: Epoxy Terrazzo pictures(Mitchell, 2008).

2.9.1 Advantages of terrazzo flooring

Durability: Terrazzo is known for its exceptional durability, making it suitable for high-traffic areas and heavy use. It can withstand the wear and tear caused by foot traffic, making it a long-lasting flooring option.

Low Maintenance: Terrazzo requires minimal maintenance, making it a practical choice for various applications. Regular cleaning and occasional resealing are typically sufficient to keep terrazzo looking its best.

Water and Heat Resistant: Terrazzo exhibits good resistance to water and heat, making it suitable for use in wet areas such as bathrooms and kitchens. It can withstand exposure to hot objects without damage.

Excellent Chemical Resistance: Terrazzo exhibits good resistance to a wide range of chemicals, making it suitable for areas where chemical spills or exposure may occur.

Slip Resistance: Terrazzo can be designed to offer good slip resistance, enhancing safety in areas prone to slip hazards, such as entrances, corridors, and wet areas.

Fast Curing: In certain terrazzo installation methods, such as epoxy terrazzo, the curing process is relatively fast, allowing for quicker project turnaround times.

Eco-Friendly: Terrazzo's potential to incorporate recycled materials, low-energy production methods, and long lifespan makes it an eco-friendly choice in sustainable construction. These properties collectively make terrazzo a desirable and reliable flooring material that is both aesthetically appealing and functional for wide range of applications(Binggeli, 2008).

2.10. White cement

Are Special cements differing from conventional Portland cements? Produced by using raw materials have low iron content that result in white. Their properties can be achieved by using a modified raw material mix, a grinding admixture or by adjusting the grinding fineness of the cement. Special cements include a number of cements whose production volumes are considerably lower compared to those of conventional cements (max. 5 to 10 %). However, they constitute a significant part of the assortment supplementing the conventional cement(Schneider *et al.*, 2011).

2.10.1 Properties of white cement

White cement is a specialized type of cement that is known for its high degree of whiteness, achieved through a modified manufacturing process that minimizes impurities like iron oxides. Beyond its color, white cement shares similar properties with grey Portland cement but often exhibits enhanced strength, fineness, and durability. It's also known for its high reflectivity and low porosity, making it suitable for a variety of decorative and functional applications. White cement is made from raw materials with a

low content of coloring elements such as Fe, Mn, Cr and Ti. Use is made of high-grade limestone or chalk containing less than 0.15 wt.% Fe₂O₃ and less than 0.015 wt.% MnO, and of white clay, kaolin or by products of its processing, and other materials which should not contain more than 1 wt.% Fe_o and 0.8 wt.% TiO₂.

Gypsum, active and inert mineral additives are introduced in (Abdelzaher *et al.*, 2023).

Why preferred to use white cement in my innovative terrazzo project? When it comes to flooring, white terrazzo floors are great materials, which are more commonly used at the present time. This flooring is made with white cement and various other raw materials that are premier in quality and reliability. White cement remains an indispensable ingredient in the construction and renovation of residential and commercial buildings. Such as, it is widely useful for producing decorative products, as well as you can also find it in rendering, precast, masonry use, street furniture, aesthetic concrete and terrazzo but in the project; little amount of white cement where used.

2.11. Tests to be performed

2.11.1 Water Absorption Test

The test for water absorption is used to determine the percentage of water that recycled terrazzo tiles absorb when exposed to moisture. The test is important in determining the resistance of the tiles to water and whether the tiles are susceptible to swelling or deforming upon contact with water. In the experiment, the tiles are first weighed when they are dry, placed in water for a given amount of time, and then weighed again after that. The difference in weight represents the water absorbed. The reading is taken as a percentage of the original dry weight of the tile. The experiment is applied to identify if the tiles can be applied under different conditions.

2.11.2 Compressive Strength Test

The compressive strength test needed in order used to determine how much pressure recycled terrazzo tiles can handle before breaking. It measures the maximum force the tiles can resist without cracking or being damaged. In this test, sample tiles are cut to standard sizes and placed in a compression testing machine. The machine slowly pressures the tile

until it breaks or is visibly distorted. The amount of pressure that the tile is able to withstand is measured and will be used to determine the compressive strength of the tile. This test is important in establishing how strong and durable the tiles are, as well as whether or not they are able to be utilized in construction applications where they have to absorb weight or pressure.

CHAPTER 3: METHODS AND MATERIALS

3.1. Study overview

This case study focuses on Ngororero District, kabaya sector in Rwanda’s Western Province, this district was selected because it provided key raw materials for the project sand and clay which were locally sourced from nearby sites. the aim was to demonstrate how eco-friendly terrazzo tiles, made from recycled plastic, glass, sand, clay, and lime, could be produced and applied locally. this case study helped evaluate the availability of raw materials, the environmental benefits of waste reuse, and the potential for community involvement in recycling and tile production. It showed that Ngororero was a suitable location for easily finding materials.

Figure 3.7: Localization of kabaya sector

3.2 Methodology

the cheap eco-friendly terrazzo tiles made from recycled plastic, glass, sand, clay, and lime with addition of little amount of cement must be manufactured. The important operations involved in this task are material selection, mixing, molding, curing, and finishing. This process ensures that the tiles are durable, aesthetically pleasing, and no harmful to the

environment. the initial step is the gathering and processing of raw materials. Recyclable trash such as plastic bottles, glass, are collected from neighborhood and while sand, and clay materials are collection from ngororero district in construction areas, and from natural near source of giciye sand swamp. The plastic wastes are cleaned, dried, and ground into very fine granules, and the glass is crushed into fine and medium-sized granules.

Sand and clay are sifted for impurity removal and lime is obtained in powder form to serve as a natural binder. Once made, the materials were mixed in appropriate proportions to provide strength and appearance. One common mix was 5-10% recycled plastic as filler, 25-30% crushed glass for strength and decoration, 17-20% sand and clay 10-15%, and 10-15% lime for bonding and durability and 5-10% cement as binder for working together with lime, clay as binder. The plastic flake was crushed to the extent state it becomes a powder and while stirring constantly, sand, clay, and crushed glass were added progressively. Finally, lime was added to improve binding and harden the mix in general.

After getting a homogeneous mixture, it was cast in pre-designed molds of standard size such as 30x25cm. The molds were compressed using hand compaction to achieve high strength and density. following molding, the tiles were left in the molds for 24-48 hours for the initial setting. They were demolded and air-dried for 7-14, 21days for additional strengthening. water curing was also employed to enhance durability through the reduction of brittleness and enhancement of resistance to environmental elements.

3.3 Methods of data collection

As mentioned previously, this project was done in three phases; field survey and observation, detailed sand exploration, manufacturing tiles made from recycled plastic, glass, lime wastes and sand lastly laboratory testing. In this section, these phases will be discussed.

3.3.1 Field survey and observations

In this first phase, enough site visits were done and detailed surveying was conducted using various surveying equipment like Bring notebooks, telephone camera, sample collection bags, and safety gear (gloves, masks, etc.). After observation the sand were suitable for use a river sand which contain low number of coarse aggregates. This field observation was important because it helped in selection of the correct type of plastic to be used. This was happened because different types of plastic crushed into powder have different physical qualities as shown in this figure3.8:

Figure 3.8: Collection of waste plastics

Based on data comes recovery-worldwide.com shows that in 2020, the use of glass products saw a significant surge, leading to a substantial increase in the amount of waste glass generated globally. According to estimates provided by the United Nations, the annual production of glass waste witnessed a 32% increase worldwide, reaching approximately 130 million tons. Moreover, in Rwanda, Nduba recycling center reported receiving a noteworthy 2-10% of the daily glass waste influx as shown in this figure 9:

Figure 3.9: Image of glasses used

Materials which were used are:

- ❖ Crushed glass waste (As marble chips, increase aesthetic and strengthening).
- ❖ Sand (fine aggregate).
- ❖ Plastic (in order to fill voids in the mixture of materials).
- ❖ Lime (color improves, economy, fire resistant and stability).
- ❖ Clay (act as a binder or filler in eco-friendly terrazzo tiles, helping in material cohesion and workability)
- ❖ White cement (binder" that holds the mixture together, creating a unique " terrazzo tile).

3.3.2 Detailed sand exploration

Giciye sand, which was collected from the Giciye River in Western Rwanda, was a clean, well-grained, and very workable material, thus an ideal material for my sustainable, low-cost terrazzo tile project. Its fine grade ensured smooth finishes, good adherence to lime and cement, and enhanced the polishing effect of the tiles. Compared to coarse sands like kayumbu, Giciye sand provided better workability, fewer impurities, and better compatibility with recycled materials like plastic, glass, clay and cement. I was able to

attain cost-effectiveness without any compromise in strength and durability by incorporating 20% Giciye sand in my mix. Though its fineness required optimal mix optimization, having a good supplier and storage made problems simpler. Together, Giciye sand enabled sustainable construction through reduced costs, better tile quality, and the use of environmentally friendly materials.

Figure 3.10: River sand (Giciye sand)

3.3.3 Detailed Lime exploration

Lime, which sourced from Musanze in Rwanda, was a strong, eco-friendly, and cheap binder for my terrazzo tile venture. With 15% hydrated lime, I enhanced binding strength, workability, and durability while achieving a smooth and durable polished surface finish. Lime was less costly and more environmentally friendly than cement, reducing production cost and environmental impact. Sourcing it from Musanze lime kilns ensured high quality. It required curing and storage appropriately to obtain the best outcome. Overall, lime improved my tile quality, rendering the project co-friendly and long-lasting.

Figure 3.11: Lime image

3.3.4 Detailed clay exploration

Clay is naturally occurring and is widely used in building and in ceramics for plasticity, strength, and bonding ability. In Rwanda, clay deposits were discovered to abound and to vary in type, and therefore to have potential for cost-effective and renewable resource utilization. As cost-effective and green building materials demands increase, physical and application parameters of local clay were vital to advance innovative technologies. This study focused on Rwandan clay's physical, processing, and potential application in low-cost, green terrazzo tiles. The types of clay, their source, and their viability for incorporation in materials such as plastic waste, glass, sand, and lime were viewed. The ideal application of clay in green tile, cost, durability, and sustainability were viewed. The result ensured that the product satisfied both economic and ecological goals as shown in this figure 3.12:

Figure 3.12: Clay Images

✓ **Performed main activities step by step:**

- Study of appropriate materials to be used.
- Terrazzo Tile mold made in timber.
- Manufacturing of proposed terrazzo tiles.
- Terrazzo Tile testing.

3.3.5 Equipment used for producing terrazzo tile

- **Weighing Scale:** A weighing scale was used to measure accurate amounts of sand, clay, cement, lime, crushed plastic, glass and amount of cement. This ensured proper proportions in the mix, leading to consistent quality and reduced material waste during production of tiles.
- **H Trowel:** The H trowel continued to be an essential tool for surface finishing in the production of terrazzo tile. It was used to evenly distribute and smooth the mixture on the surface of the terrazzo, ensuring a uniform and desirable finish. The use of the H trowel helped prevent any potential injuries during the surface finishing process.
- **Personal Protective Equipment (PPE):** Throughout the process, personal protective equipment such as gloves, masks, goggles, and boots was used to ensure worker safety, especially during crushing, mixing, and polishing activities.
- **Curing bucket:** After compaction, the tiles were cured using regular water spraying. This maintained moisture during the curing period, allowing the tiles to gain strength and durability while preventing cracking.
- **Polishing Machine or Grinder:** Once the tiles were cured, a polishing machine was used to smooth and refine the surface. This process exposed the decorative elements and gave the tiles a glossy and attractive finish.
- **Trowel:** The trowel was used as a handheld tool with a flat steel blade and handle, designed to spread, level, smooth, and finish the recycled terrazzo mixture inside

the tile molds. It played a crucial role in ensuring that the mixture was evenly distributed across the mold surface, compacted properly to eliminate air pockets, and smoothed to create a uniform, level finish. This careful manual troweling process contributed significantly to the overall surface quality, dimensional accuracy, and aesthetic appearance of the finished terrazzo tiles.

3.4 Quantity of materials used

Table 3.4: Quantities of composition of manufactured terrazzo tile (25cm*20cm*1.5cm)

Materials	Type	Quantity in % and (kg)
Glasses	Recycled glasses	30% or 0.700kg
Sand	River	20% or 0.250 kg
lime	Hydrated lime	15% or 0.142kg
Plastic	Plastic powder	10% or 0.125 kg
Clay	Hydrated clay	15% or 0.145kg
White cement	Hydrated	10% or 0.120 kg
Water	workable	1l

3.4.1 Terrazzo tile samples preparation

This stage deals with the manufacturing of terrazzo tiles made from recycled plastic, glasses, lime, clay and sand to be used in finishing purpose especially on the floors. The measurements of this terrazzo tile are according to the formwork used which had measurements of (25*20*1.5cm). the decision of selecting thickness was based on recommended by **EN 13748-1** for standard indoor flooring (10-15 mm) and **EN 13748-2** for outdoor use (15–30 mm), it was selected for experimental purposes.

3.4.2 Procedures of manufacturing terrazzo tile

- **Design and Planning:** Determine the desired design, color scheme, and pattern for the terrazzo tiles. Calculate the required quantities of materials based on the dimensions and thickness of the tiles. So, Prepared the molds or forms needed for casting the tiles.

Figure 3.13: Formation of mold

- **Washing:** the glasses chips were then washed to remove paper labels, dust and any remnants of the products they once contained. in this stage a bucket was used for washing sand and glasses.

Figure 3.14: Preparation of crushed glasses into two ways

- **Material Preparation:** Clean and prepare the glass aggregates, ensuring they are free from contaminants, crushed it within two different ways; first one was to crushed it with size of less than 1 mm to be added in the mixture to increase strength and the second one was larger pieces of crushed glass with sizes ranging from 3 mm to 5 mm were used as decorative aggregates in the surface layer of the terrazzo tile. Hydrate the lime according to the manufacturer's instructions then Check the quality and consistency of the materials. Preparation of sand, clay and plastic powder to ensure it is clean and well graded.
- **Batching:** In this stage, carefully determination of the appropriate mixing ratios of crushed glass, recycled plastic, clay, sand, lime, and a small quantity of white cement to produce terrazzo tiles with optimal performance and aesthetic appeal according to the quantities mentioned above. The goal is to balance the structural integrity, workability, and eco-friendliness of the mixture. Crushed glass contributes to hardness and decorative appearance; plastic helps reduce voids and increase sustainability; clay and lime act as binding agents to enhance strength and reduce the need for conventional cement; sand provides bulk and texture; and white cement is added in small quantities to improve the binding quality and provide a brighter finish. Each material is weighed or volumetrically measured according to a predefined mix design to ensure consistency, durability, and visual uniformity in the final terrazzo tile product.
- **Crushed plastic:** In this step, crushed plastic particles were prepared to help in fill the voids between the larger components (such as sand, glass, and clay) and improve the overall packing density of the terrazzo mixture. The plastic used was processed into a fine powder form, with particle sizes ranging approximately between 0.5 mm to 1 mm, ensuring it could effectively act as a filler material. This addition not only contributed to reducing material porosity but also enhanced the sustainability of the tiles by incorporating recycled plastic waste.

Figure 3.15: Crushed plastics sample

- **Mixing the Terrazzo Mixtures:** Measure and combine the appropriate ratios of plastic powder, clay, lime, sand, little amount of cement and crushed glasses in a mixing container and addition of water. Mix the materials thoroughly until they are well blended and homogeneous. This done manually with a shovel or mechanically mixer.

Figure 3.16: Mixture of terrazzo materials

- **Casting and Compaction:** After thoroughly mixing the terrazzo components including crushed glass, recycled plastic, sand, clay, lime, and a small amount of white cement, mixture was poured into the prepared molds, ensuring even distribution to avoid weak spots or uneven thickness. Then, the use a trowel to compact the mixture firmly, eliminating air pockets and improving the overall strength and bonding of the materials. After compaction, leveled was applied in order to make the surface using H trowel to achieve a smooth and uniform finish.

- **Curing:** Curing is a vital step in terrazzo tile production, as it ensures proper hydration of cement and directly affects the final strength and durability of the tile. In this study, Allow the terrazzo tiles to be cured over a 21-day period, with performance assessments conducted at 7, 14, and 21 days. A wet curing method was used by covering the tiles with plastic sheets to prevent moisture loss and support continuous hydration. Results showed that compressive strength increased consistently with curing time, confirming the effectiveness of the process. This demonstrated that proper curing not only enhances tile performance but is especially important when using recycled materials like glass and plastic.

Figure 3.17: Curing process image

- **Grinding and Polishing:** Once the terrazzo tiles have sufficiently cured, remove them from the molds or forms. Grind the surface of the tiles using progressively finer abrasive pads or grinding stones to achieve the desired level of smoothness and expose the glass aggregates. Polish the tiles using polishing pads and grinding machine to enhance the shine and luster of the surface.

Figure 3.18: Grinding image

- **Finishing:** Clean the terrazzo tiles thoroughly to remove any dust or residue from the grinding and polishing process. Inspect the tiles for any imperfections and make any necessary repairs or touch-ups. Apply a protective sealer to enhance the durability and stain resistance of the tiles.

Figure 3.19: Spraying varnishing on finished terrazzo tile

- **Final products:** The final terrazzo tile was produced by combining recycled materials such as plastic, glass, sand, lime, clay with a little amount of cement. After casting, curing, and polishing, the tile revealed a smooth, attractive surface with a

distinctive mosaic of colorful fragments. It achieved excellent durability, wear resistance, and aesthetic appeal, making it suitable for use in flooring, walls, and decorative applications. Each tile became a unique, eco-friendly product that helped reduce environmental waste while offering a high-quality, sustainable building material, but this project is designed to be used inside floor in the building.

Figure 3.20: New terrazzo tiles images

3.5. Cost assessment

cost analysis was conducted as part of the study survey. This involved comparing the total material costs required to produce one square meter of each tile type. In traditional terrazzo production, marble chippings are a major component and significantly contribute to high production costs, with one bag of 50 kg costing approximately 60,000 Rwandan Francs (RWF). This cost estimation was confirmed through a market survey conducted with terrazzo tile manufacturers and material sellers. In contrast, the recycled terrazzo tiles in this study utilized crushed waste glass and plastic, which are either freely sourced or obtained at minimal cost from local waste collection centers. The cost assessment focused on raw material expenses, availability, and the potential savings associated with substituting expensive conventional aggregates with recycled alternatives. This analysis helped demonstrate the economic advantage of using recycled materials while maintaining functional and aesthetic performance.

3.6. Environmental impacts analysis

the methods used to achieve the objectives of the study on the environmental impact assessment of the terrazzo tiles. Special attention was given to the use of recycled materials such as plastic, glass, and sand, in comparison to conventional terrazzo tile production methods. The environmental evaluation was guided by recognized international standards, as interpreted from academic and technical literature, with reference to data gathered from books, research publications, and standard guidelines, simplified **Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)** approach. This was guided by **ISO 14040** and **ISO 14044** standards as interpreted from academic books and literature sources such as (Materials Science Forum for recent LCA developments in recycled glass composites academic journal and Curran's Handbook, Hauschild's text, etc..). The goal was to evaluate and compare the environmental impacts of recycled terrazzo tile production and traditional terrazzo manufacturing, focusing on resource use, emissions, waste, and sustainability performance.

3.7 Laboratory tests conducted on the specimens

the laboratory tests are conducted in order to know the quality of the final product, helps in making comparison between the new product with the existing products, also tests on new product are done in order to check whether it will meet with the requirements of the regulatory agencies and tests helps in evaluating product design or improvement specifications. The tests conducted on this terrazzo tile are of the following.

3.7.1 Water absorption test

Water absorption test of recycled plastics, glasses, clay, lime and sand with addition of little amount of cement to make terrazzo tile was conducted in order to determine the amount of water absorbed by them when subjected to extreme conditions. The absorption test could be used as indicator of durability properties of these tiles and behavior of them in weathering condition.

The water absorptivity of a composite sample was investigated using a standard procedure. Initially, the composite sample was prepared and cut into appropriate dimensions for testing the specimens used 14x14x1.5cm. The samples were conditioned in a controlled

environment to ensure consistent moisture content. To initiate the water absorption test, three samples were taken from each mass fraction of the composite material for terrazzo tile and also two samples for traditional tile were tested. The initial weights of these samples were recorded before starting the experiment.

Next, the samples were immersed in water for various time of 24 hours. The immersion took place at room temperature, typically maintained at 25°C. The purpose of the 24 hours was to observe how the samples can absorb water over an extended period. After that, the samples were removed from the water and carefully cleaned to remove any excess surface moisture. Then, they were dried using a suitable method to eliminate any residual water content.

Once the samples were completely dry, their final weights were measured. These weights were recorded and mass fraction, providing data on the amount of water absorbed by the composite material for each specimen, I mean terrazzo tile and traditional tile samples. To calculate the percentage water absorptivity (WAC) for each and mass fraction, the following formula was used:

$$\text{WAC} = (\text{Weight at a given time} - \text{Initial weight}) / (\text{Initial weight}) * 100\%$$

$$W = \frac{m_2 - m_1}{m_1} * 100$$

Where:

W: was the water absorption percentage (%).

M1: was dry mass of terrazzo tile (the mass in g of oven dried tile in air).

M2: was the mass of terrazzo tile immersed in water (the mass in g)

By applying this formula to the recorded data, the water absorptivity of the composite material could be determined and mass fractions. This information is essential for understanding the material's water resistance, dimensional stability, and other relevant properties relevant to its potential applications. The results help to assess the suitability of

the composite for various environmental conditions and guide the development of new materials or improvements to existing ones.

Apparatus required

- samples of terrazzo tiles
- Laboratory oven
- Plastic bucket and test equipment
- Electronic weighing balance

The objective

The objectives of doing water absorption test were to determine the amount of water absorbed by tile.

Figure 3.21: Electronic weighed balance and soaking tile process to ensure water absorption

3.7.2 Compressive strength test of terrazzo tile

Compressive test this was conducted to determine the compressive strength of tiles. In other word was termed as crushing strength of tiles. Generally, three tile specimens were taken to laboratory for testing and tested individually and two specimens for traditional tile also were tested. In this test, a specimen of tiles was put on crushing machine and loaded pressure until it is crushed. The ultimate pressure at which tile was crushed were taken into account. All three tile specimens were tested separately and average result was taken as tile compressive crushing strength,

Purpose: Measures the strength required to break the tile.

Noted that: A tile is placed under a press, and pressure is applied until it crushes.

Figure 3.22: Test procedure checking compressive strength of tile

3.7.2.1 Apparatus used

The required equipment and apparatus used in compressive strength of terrazzo tile were: an electronic weighing balance, a vibrating Needle, and compression testing machine, gloves. Apparatus was used for achieving compression test were followed: compression-testing machine, specimen (tile) and calculation of compressive strength of specimen should calculated by taking maximum load in newton (N) divided by plan area in millimeter (mm^2) the strength was expressed in N/mm^2 .

3.7.2.2 The procedure used

The goal of a compression test was to determine the behavior of material while it experiences a compressive load measuring fundamental variables such as, strain, stress and deformation this was important because it help to know the resistance of tile under compression force and other external applied force.

The compressive strength test was carried out in accordance with the specifications. The specimen was cast into cubical sizes of 14x14x1.5cm before being placed on compression machine with 2000 KN capacity. Three samples were tested for terrazzo tile and two samples for traditional tile were also tested for each replacement specimens and the average value was determined. The samples were placed on the machine platen and loaded until crushed. The compressive strength C_s was calculated. from

$$C_s = \frac{F}{A} \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where F in (N) is the failure load, A is the area of the samples in (Cm²) respectively

CHAPTER 4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This chapter present the interpretation and discussion of the results of this project of study and manufacturing of tile from wastes recycled plastic, glasses, lime, clay, sand and little amount of cement hence comparison between the proposed products with the existing ones.

Based on the row material collected, the mix proportions were designated with appropriate ratios. Terrazzo Tile specimen was cast according to the mix proportions planned. After, the terrazzo tile specimens were tested for its compressive strength and water absorption. The compressive strength for sample A1 and A2 were found to be satisfactory with respect to their compressive strength, Water absorption was found to be satisfactory.

4.1 Analyses of water absorption Test

The water absorptivity of the composite material was investigated through a series of water absorption tests conducted at room temperature (25°C) and various time intervals. three samples for terrazzo tile and two samples for traditional tile were taken from each mass fraction of the composite material, and their initial weights were recorded before immersing them in water. specimen of each composition was tested for their initial dry weight (M1) and final wet weight (M2) for 24 hours. The percentage of absorption of water into the material was computed using the formula:

Table 4.5: Result of estimated percentage absorption of the Terrazzo tile

No	Specimen	Weight of the tile after immersion(g)	Weight of tile before absorbed water(g)	Percentage absorption (%)	Average
1	A1	707.6	720.5	1.82	1.70±0.55
2	A2	798.1	815.6	2.19	
3	A3	602.4	609.6	1.11	

Figure 4.23: Graph that shows water absorption within specimen

The results show that the percentage of water absorption increases as the amounts of waste glass, plastic, sand, clay, and lime in the terrazzo tile increase. If we want to add more waste plastic, sand, and clay to produce stronger tiles, we may have to accept higher water absorption as a trade-off.

According to the results in Table 4.5 and Figure 4.23, the estimated water absorption percentage for terrazzo tiles made from recycled glass, plastic, lime, sand, and clay rises over time as the tiles stay submerged in water. Eventually, the tiles reach a saturation point where the water absorption percentage levels off and stops increasing. It's important to note that the tile's composition plays a key role in how much water it absorbs. For example, a higher amount of clay in the mix can lead to greater water absorption. This information is essential for deciding where and how the terrazzo tiles can be used effectively.

Table 4.6: Result of estimated percentage absorption of the traditional tile

No	Specimen	Weight of the tile after immersion(g)	Weight of tile before absorbed water(g)	Percentage absorption (%)	Average
1	A1	764.5	777.2	1.66	1.92±0.37
2	A2	782.2	799.3	2.18	

Figure 4.24: Graph that shows water absorption within specimen

Discussion:

Comparison between terrazzo tile and traditional tile the water absorption test showed that the developed terrazzo tile achieved a water absorption of $1.7\pm 0.55\%$, while the traditional tile had $1.92\pm 0.37\%$. According to ASTM standards (such as ASTM C373), tiles with water absorption below 3% are classified as low-porosity and are considered highly resistant to water. This indicates that the terrazzo tile not only meets but performs better than the traditional tile in terms of water resistance, making it suitable for both indoor and outdoor applications but according to the thickness of that terrazzo tile products it's recommended to be used indoor. These results highlight the effectiveness of incorporating plastic, glass, clay, sand, lime, and little amount of cement in improving the tile's performance.

4.2. Result for determining compression test

This test were helpers to know the compressive strength of the tile made from recycled plastic, glass waste, lime, clay and sand. This was called crushing strength of tile. Generally, three specimens of terrazzo tile were taken into laboratory for testing and two specimens for traditional tile were also taken into laboratory for testing. In this test, a tile specimen was put on compressive testing machine and applied pressure until it breaks. The ultimate pressure at which tile was crushed were taken into account. The tile specimen was tested and the average result were taken as tile's compressive /crushing strength, the volume of a specimen was (14× 14×1.5 cm).

Table 4.7: Compressive strength results for new terrazzo tile within 7days, 14days and 21days

% of water	7 days of curing			14 days of curing			21 days of curing		
	KN	MPa	Average	KN	MPa	Average	KN	MPa	Average
20%	1221.3	62.30	62.08±0.62	1371.3	69.97	69.57 ±0.65	1321.5	72.52	68.83± 1.2
	1211.6	61.79		1372.2	70.02		1369.2	69.86	
	1218.3	62.15		1347.4	68.73		1356.3	69.199	
30%	1343.5	68.49	68.58±0.09	1371.3	69.97	69.82 ±0.77	1461.4	74.57	72.06± 2.1
	1345.3	68.58		1358.7	69.33		1341.9	68.56	
	1346.2	68.67		1341.3	68.433		1431.4	73.03	
40%	1298.3	67.35	65.28±1.19	1251.8	63.88	66.96 6±2.5 5	1311.2	66.88	65.66± 1.07
	1277.3	65.17		1345.3	68.58		1277.3	65.17	
	1241.2	63.32		1341.6	68.44		1272.4	64.92	

Table 4.8: 7days Compressive strength of crushed glass under different ratio

Crushed glass %	Specimen	Weight of specimen (g)	Volume (Cm)	crushing load (KN)	Load average (KN)	Pressure (MPa)	Average pressure (MPa)
20%	A1	598.3	14*14*1.5	1221.3	1217.0667	62.30	62.08±0.62
	A2	565.8	14*14*1.5	1211.6		61.79	
	A3	583.4	14*14*1.5	1218.3		62.15	
30%	A1	605.2	14*14*1.5	1343.5	1345	68.49	68.58±0.09
	A2	656.4	14*14*1.5	1345.3		68.58	
	A3	689.3	14*14*1.5	1346.2		68.67	
40%	A1	707.6	14*14*1.5	1298.3	1272.267	67.35	65.28±1.19
	A2	721.4	14*14*1.5	1277.3		65.17	
	A3	735.3	14*14*1.5	1241.2		63.32	

Figure 4.25: 7days Compressive strength of crushed glass under different ratios

The results obtained after 7 days of curing showed a clear trend in the compressive strength of that terrazzo tile with different crushed glass percentages. the control sample (Crushed glass =20%) had a compressive strength of 62.08 ± 0.62 MPa. for (Crushed glass =30%), the compressive strength increased to 68.58 ± 0.09 MPa showing improved strength so, for (Crushed glass =40%) the compressive strength decreases to 65.28 ± 1.19 MPa, means at the (Crushed glass =30%) the compressive strength increase.

Table 4.9: 14days Compressive strength of crushed glass under different ratio

Crushed glass %	Specimen	Weight of specimen (g)	Volume (Cm)	crushing load (KN)	Load average (KN)	Pressure (MPa)	Average pressure (MPa)
20%	A1	598.3	14*14*1.5	1371.3	1363.633	69.97	69.57±0.65
	A2	565.8	14*14*1.5	1372.2		70.02	
	A3	583.4	14*14*1.5	1347.4		68.73	
30%	A1	603.2	14*14*1.5	1371.3	1367.22	69.97	69.82±0.77
	A2	655.4	14*14*1.5	1358.7		69.33	
	A3	688.3	14*14*1.5	1341.3		68.433	
40%	A1	702.6	14*14*1.5	1251.8	1312.9	63.88	66.966±2.55
	A2	711.4	14*14*1.5	1345.3		68.58	
	A3	734.3	14*14*1.5	1341.6		68.44	

Figure 4.26: 14days Compressive strength of crushed glass under different ratios

The results obtained after 14 days of curing showed a clear trend in the compressive strength of that terrazzo tile with different crushed glass percentages. The control sample (Crushed glass =20%) had a compressive strength of 69.57 ± 0.65 MPa and (Crushed glass =30%), the compressive strength increased to 69.82 ± 0.77 MPa showing improved strength so, for (Crushed glass =40%) the compressive strength decreases to 66.966 ± 2.55 MPa, means at the (Crushed glass =30%) the compressive strength increase.

Table 4.10: 21days Compressive strength of crushed glass under different ratio

Crushed glass %	Specimen	Weight of specimen (g)	Volume (Cm)	Applied load (KN)	Load average (KN)	Pressure (MPa)	Average pressure (MPa)
20%	A1	596.3	14*14*1.5	1321.5	1349	67.432	68.83±1.2
	A2	566.8	14*14*1.5	1369.2		69.86	
	A3	584.4	14*14*1.5	1356.3		69.199	
30%	A1	604.2	14*14*1.5	1461.4	1411.566	74.57	72.06±2.1
	A2	657.4	14*14*1.5	1341.9		68.56	
	A3	687.3	14*14*1.5	1431.4		73.03	
40%	A1	706.6	14*14*1.5	1311.2	1286.966	66.89	65.66±1.07
	A2	722.4	14*14*1.5	1277.3		65.168	
	A3	734 .3	14*14*1.5	1272.4		64.92	

Figure 4.27: 21days Compressive strength of crushed glass under different ratios

The results obtained after 21 days of curing showed a clear trend in the compressive strength of that terrazzo tile with different crushed glass%. The control sample (Crushed glass =20%) had a compressive strength of 68.83 MPa and (Crushed glass =30%), the compressive strength increased to 72.06 ± 2.1 MPa showing improved strength so, for (Crushed glass =40%) the compressive strength decreases to 65.66 ± 1.07 MPa, means at the (Crushed glass =30%) the compressive strength increase.

Table 4.11: Compressive strength of traditional tile

N°	Curing period	Weight of specimen (g)	Volume of tile (Cm)	Applied load (KN)	Compressive strength (MPa)	Average
1	7days	515.2	14×14×1.5	1241.3	63.33	64.25±1.3
2		519.3	14×14×1.5	1277.3	65.17	
1	14 days	533.1	14×14×1.5	1347.2	68.73	66.582±1.6
2		524.4	14×14×1.5	1264.7	64.452	
1	21days	530.1	14×14×1.5	1334.4	68.08	67.505±0.81
2		522.23	14×14×1.5	1311.9	66.93	

Figure 4.28: Chart that shows Compressive strength

Table 4.11 shows the specific compressive strength values for the traditional tile content at different curing periods (7 days, 14 days, and 21 days). The compressive strength values in MPa are given as 64.25 ± 1.3 , 66.582 ± 1.6 , 67.505 ± 0.81 and for 7 days, 14 days, and 21 days of curing, respectively. Figure 4.28 provides a graphical representation of the compressive strength results for the traditional terrazzo tile. At the 21 days the compressive strength increased, so according to ASTM standards (such as ASTM C373) this 67.505 MPa is good.

Discussion:

Comparison between terrazzo tile and traditional terrazzo tile the compression strength test showed that the developed terrazzo tile achieved a strength of 72.06 ± 2.1 MPa, while the traditional tile had 67.505 ± 0.81 MPa. According to ASTM standards (such as ASTM C373), terrazzo tiles with compressional strength below 20 MPa are classified as low-compressive strength and are considered highly affected to cracking and fail during installation. This indicates that the terrazzo tile not only meets but performs better than the traditional tile in terms of compressive strength, making it suitable for both indoor and outdoor applications but according to the thickness of that terrazzo tile products it's recommended to be used indoor. These results highlight the effectiveness of incorporating plastic, glass, clay, sand, lime, and little amount of cement in improving the tile's performance.

4.3 Comparison between traditional terrazzo tile and new terrazzo tile

Based on the results, found that the traditional terrazzo tile is made from cement or epoxy resin combined with marble or granite chips, which make it expensive and environmentally harmful due to cement production and mining. In comparison, the eco-friendly terrazzo tiles the developed use of recycled plastic, glass for decoration and strengthening tile and sand, little amount of cement, lime, and clay as binder's materials are cheaper, more sustainable, locally available. the final product is lighter, has a unique appearance, and helps reduce plastic and glass waste. The eco-friendly version still shows good strength and durability when properly processed.

Table 4.12: Comparison between the new terrazzo tile and traditional terrazzo tiles

Terrazzo tile (traditional product)	Terrazzo Tile (new product)
Relies on non-recycled aggregates have impacts on environment	Is environment friendly with recycled glass, plastic and eco-friendly materials.
Use natural stones which can be more expensive like quartz, pearls...	Cost effective due to use of recycled materials such as glass, plastic, lime, clay...
Have more options of choosing more natural stone aggregates	Offers unique aesthetic with recycled glasses

Table 4.13: Comparison of results found between the new terrazzo tile and traditional terrazzo tiles

N°	Test	New terrazzo	Traditional terrazzo	Observation
1	Water absorption	1.7±0.55%	1.92±0.37%	New terrazzo absorbs less water due to improved material such as crushed plastics and glass compared to traditional terrazzo according to international standard above 3% considered as terrazzo tile has high level of water absorption.
2	Compressive strength test	72.06±2.1Mpa (at 30% crushed glasses within 21days curing period)	67.505±0.81Mpa (within 21days curing period)	New terrazzo shows better strength from added recycled plastic and glass particles compared to traditional terrazzo. International confirming that below 20Mpa the terrazzo tile considered as low-compressive strength.

4.4 Cost assessment

The cost analysis showed a clear difference in material expenses between recycled terrazzo tiles and traditional terrazzo tiles. Traditional terrazzo tiles mainly depend on marble chippings, which are costly and significantly increase the overall production cost. Market surveys with local terrazzo producers indicated that one bag of 50 kg of the marble chippings costs about 60,000 Rwandan Francs (RWF) and also the local market price for that traditional terrazzo tile cost is 40,000Rwf/m².

This makes marble the most expensive component in the traditional mix. On the other hand, the recycled terrazzo tiles used crushed waste glass and plastic as alternative aggregates. These materials were obtained from local waste sources at little to no cost, which greatly reduced the overall expenses. The use of other locally available materials like sand, clay, and lime also helped minimize reliance on expensive inputs.

4.5 Environmental Impact Analysis

The environmental impact analysis of the terrazzo tile production process was investigated in accordance with ISO 14040 and ISO 14044 standards for Life Cycle Assessment (LCA). The results demonstrated that the incorporation of recycled materials specifically plastic, glass, and sand significantly reduced the environmental footprint compared to conventional terrazzo tiles. The use of recycled plastic and glass reduced the demand for virgin raw materials and minimized landfill waste. Carbon emissions were notably lower due to reduced energy consumption during raw material processing. The locally sourced sand, clay, and lime further contributed to lowering transportation related emissions.

Water usage and energy input during manufacturing remained within acceptable limits, aligning with the environmental performance indicators set by ISO 14001. Moreover, no hazardous by products were recorded during production, and waste generation was minimal and manageable. Overall, the production process achieved improved sustainability performance while maintaining quality, with 60% reduction in estimated carbon footprint compared to traditional terrazzo tiles.

CHAPTER 5: CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1. Conclusion

This study addressed the global challenge of managing plastic and glass waste by promoting their innovative reuse in the production of eco-friendly terrazzo tiles. The developed tiles, composed of recycled glass, plastic waste, sand, lime, clay, and a small amount of cement, demonstrated promising results in key performance areas. The water absorption capacity of the new terrazzo tile (dimensions: 25 cm × 20 cm × 1.5 cm) was found to be $1.70 \pm 0.55\%$, which is lower than the $1.92 \pm 0.37\%$ measured in traditional terrazzo tiles and well within the ASTM standard threshold of 3%. This confirms the suitability of the new tile in terms of water resistance.

Additionally, compressive strength tests were conducted using various ratios of crushed glass (20%, 30%, and 40%) over different curing periods (7, 14, and 21 days). The results revealed compressive strengths ranging from 62.08 ± 0.62 N/mm² to 72.06 ± 2.1 N/mm², which exceed those of traditional terrazzo tiles (64.25 ± 1.3 to 67.505 ± 0.81 N/mm²) and are significantly higher than the minimum strength required to avoid cracking or failure during installation (20 MPa, as per ASTM C373). This demonstrates that the new terrazzo tiles are not only environmentally friendly but also structurally strong and reliable. From an economic perspective, the new terrazzo tiles are cost-effective, with an estimated price of 30,000 RWF/m² compared to the traditional market price of 40,000 RWF/m², enhancing their affordability and feasibility in construction projects.

In conclusion, this project highlights the potential for turning waste materials into high-performance construction products. It is recommended that future research explore additional performance characteristics such as fire resistance, slip resistance, and tensile strength, which could not be assessed in this study due to limited access to specialized laboratories materials.

5.2 Recommendations

I would like to recommend the Republic of Rwanda, to provide all necessary manners for getting the resource or finding the investors in order to perform this project. On other hand the researchers are also recommended to give their contribution on this project by working on remaining items such as fire resistance, tensile test, etc. and also other recommendation is to tell the REMA to establish more glasses, plastics waste disposals in order to collect those wastes easily at least in every district.

Furthermore, it is recommended to the other students of INES-Ruhengeri and others students from higher learning institution to use the findings from this research for the further studies allocated. I also recommend construction companies such as MARCELO REAL ESTATE and DATA PLANET INNOVATION COMPANY to support me for implementing this project and place it in the market.

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APPENDICES

Appendix A: Cost estimation and bill of quantity of one terrazzo tile

Number	Item	quantity	Unit price	Amount (Rwf)
1	form work	1	1000frw/20tiles	50
2	White Cement cost	0.250kg	1000frw/kg	250
3	Glasses	0.700kg	40frw/kg	28
4	Lime	0.142kg	800frw/kg	113.6
5	Sand	0.250kg	500frw/kg	125
6	Clay	0.145kg	70frw/kg	10.15
7	Water	1l	20frw/l	20
8	Polish and applying varnish	1l	5000frw/40 tiles	125frw
9	Grinding and Sanding paper	1	3000frw/30tiles	100frw
10	Labor cost	1 labor	1100frw/3tiles in hour	360frw
11	Plastic	0.125 kg	800frw/kg	100
Total: 1300Rwf				

TOOLS					
II	Description of item	Unit	Quantity	Rate/Rwf	Total (Rwf)
1	H trowel	piece	1	2500	2500
2	Tape measure	piece	1	700	700
3	Trowel	piece	1	1500	1500
Total					4700
TRANSPORT					
10,000					
General Total					
14,700					

It means that, production cost of one new terrazzo tile is 1300Rwf but it's supposed to be sold on 1500frw, while the cost of existing one on the market is 2000Rwf on the same size.

Manufactured terrazzo tiles are proposed to be 30,000Rwf/m², while the local market price show that traditional terrazzo cost is 40,000Rwf/m².

Appendix B: ALL SET SUPPLY LTD Terrazzo tile proof of amount

ALLSET SUPPLY LTD
P.O. Box:112 Kigali, Nyarugenge
Tel: +250780548777
Email:ngirinshuti44@gmail.com

Date:20, June, 2025

To Whom It May Concern

Subject: Price Confirmation of Terrazzo Tiles

This is to confirm that ALLSET SUPPLY LTD currently supplies terrazzo floor tiles at a market price of **Forty Thousand Rwandan Francs (40,000 RWF) per square meter (1m²)**.
This price represents the typical design and quality widely used in the construction sector and corresponds to standard market expectations. Kindly note that the cost may fluctuate based on custom design choices, colour variations, and the quantity ordered.
This letter is issued as an official confirmation for reference regarding pricing.
For any additional details or inquiries, feel free to reach out to us.

Sincerely,

NGIRINSHUTI EGIDE
Owner of company
ALLSET SUPPLY LTD
+250780454238
Email: ngirinshuti44@gmail.com

Company Stamp / Signature:

Appendix C: RG Tech solution ltd terrazzo tile proof of amount

Appendix D: To whom it may concern

